

Introduction

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This number of *Mycologia Balcanica* is devoted to fungal conservation and, in particular, to a special meeting on the topic held in October 2009 at the Whitby Museum, Whitby, North Yorkshire, UK. The objective of that meeting, funded by the Mohamed Bin Zayed Species Conservation Fund and the UK Darwin Initiative, was to raise awareness among mycologists of three key elements of fungal conservation: science, infrastructure and politics.

If the history of the conservation movement, up to now, is imagined as a folk story, then fungi have undoubtedly played the part of Cinderella. Overlooked by mainstream conservationists interested only in vertebrates and flowering plants, the fungi have received a raw deal. The provisions of the Rio *Convention on Biological Diversity* have singularly failed to protect the fungi, so much so that mycologists now openly talk of fungi as being the “orphans of Rio”, excluded from family decisions and deprived of the support enjoyed by their animal and plant relatives. There has thus been growing dissatisfaction among mycologists about the neglect of fungal conservation, and that dissatisfaction has been accompanied by an increasingly strong desire to do something about it.

The twelve months preceding the Whitby meeting, were important for fungal conservation. The *International Union for Conservation of Nature* [IUCN] made a highly significant reform of its *Species Survival Commission* [SSC] so that, for the first time, fungi were properly represented, as an independent group separate from animals and plants, and the number of specialist committees covering fungi more than doubled. In South America, a steering committee was appointed to establish a fungal conservation group within the *Asociación Latino-Americana de Micología*. The *African Mycological Association*, the *Mycological Society of America* (representing North America), and the *Asian Mycology Committee* went one step further and each established their own fungal conservation group. Taken with the existing

fungal conservation groups for Australasia and Europe, this meant that for the first time all inhabited continents had their own clusters of mycologists interested in protecting fungi. As a result, the Whitby meeting was timely, occurring as it did on the cusp of rapid change.

Like its predecessor, the first global meeting on fungal conservation, held in Córdoba, Spain in December 2007, the Whitby meeting was attended by mycologists and conservationists from many countries. Unlike its predecessor, however, the Whitby meeting was able to host representatives of each continental-level conservation group, and each IUCN SSC fungal specialist group, making its deliberations more structured and representative. There were even voices for fungi of Antarctica and the oceans. Where the Córdoba meeting looked at sustainable use of fungi, the single most important result of the Whitby meeting was the ground-breaking decision to establish a global federation of fungal conservation groups.

The team appointed by the Whitby meeting to bring that about then set up a third special meeting, held at the Royal Botanic Garden, Edinburgh on 6 August 2010, at the same time as (but separate from) the 9th *International Mycological Congress*. The purpose of that further special meeting was not only to discuss the draft constitution of this federation, but also to do something concrete: the happy result was the founding of the *International Society for Fungal Conservation*, the world's first society explicitly devoted to protecting fungi. That society is now, like a small child, taking its first steps. In particular, a domain name has been registered on its behalf, and it now has a website, www.fungal-conservation.org where more information about its activities can be found.

This is an exciting development which could not have occurred without the labours of a generation of far-sighted mycologists dedicated to the idea that fungi too need protection. While it is not possible to name all here, it would

be wrong to pass without recognition of at least a few. Names which spring to mind - and this is just for conservation *sensu stricto* - include: Eef Arnolds, Anders Bohlin, Paco Calonge, Mike Castellano, Regis Courtecuisse, Anders Dahlberg, Shelley Evans, Bruce Ing, Heikki Kotiranta, Sasha Kovalenko, Maria Ławrynowicz, Tom May, Julio Mena Portales, David Moore, Baldomero Moreno Arroyo, Marijka Nauta, David Pegler, Claudia Perini, Maurice Rotheroe, Christoph Scheidegger, Beatrice Senn-Irlet, Jim Trappe, Giuseppe Venturella and Roy Watling. To recognize the contributions of those who have worked in the broader arena of fungal biodiversity, the list would be far larger.

Given the fluid and rapidly changing situation in fungal conservation, this special number of *Mycologia Balcanica* should be regarded as no more than a snapshot in time of some issues and views which were being discussed by fungal conservationists towards the end of the 2000s. The snapshot is tantalizing. It is incomplete. The overwhelming impression is of gaps. Each contribution is like a tiny island in an ocean of absent resources. There are accomplished reviews of the state of fungal conservation in Antarctica, Australia and New Zealand, and the very first attempt to do something similar for a West African country. The issues of sustainable harvesting and the need for political will in lobbying are identified, with examples from Egypt and Greece. An eloquent argument

is made for the important role of culture collections for ex situ conservation. Problems facing the poorest countries of Africa in addressing fungal conservation are described. The application of computerized databases is discussed from the context of fungal conservation in Switzerland. The planned activities of two of the new IUCN fungal specialist groups are outlined.

Taking another simile, this work is like a dancing bear - remarkable not because it dances well, but because it dances at all. But that is no more than the reality of the current situation. We see enthusiasts with vision and ambition to make a real change to the world's conservation movement, which at present seems almost entirely unaware that fungi might be important. Among these pages, whole regions, indeed whole continents are unrepresented, and for many fungal groups, there is little or no information at all. The contributions range from the sophisticated to tentative and basic first steps. But in many cases, what is amazing is that there are any contributions at all.

The take-home message from this introduction is therefore not to doubt the direction, the determination or vigour of this publication. Fungal conservation is here to stay, and not just to stay, but to develop and take its place alongside animal and plant conservation as an equal partner, equally important and equally valued. Only in that way can we really adopt an ecosystem approach to conservation.